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Research Article

CHARACTERISTICS AND OUTCOME REGARDING SURVIVAL OF DIFFUSE LARGE B-CELL LYMPHOMA PATIENTS WITH CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM RELAPSES

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Abstract:

Objective: Relapses of Central Nervous System of Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma are not common and these are nearly fatal. Two-year risk of central nervous system relapse is 0.8% in low, 3.9% in medium and 12.0% in the patients of high risk. This research work aimed to determine the baseline traits and outcome regarding the median rate of survival of the patients of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma present with relapse of central nervous system.

Methodology: This study is a retrospective research work. All patients of diffuse large b-cell lymphoma with relapse of Central Nervous System from 2012 to 2019 were the part of this research work. We collected the information from the database of the hospital to analyze the median rate of survival and relevant characteristics.

Results: 21 patients were the part of this research work, in which 66.3% (n: 14) were males and 33.7% (n: 7) were female patients. There was gut of extra-nodal sites in 9.1% (n: 2) whereas 4.5% (n: 1) patient with the involvement of these organs was present; cervix, iliac bone, gluteal muscle, ovaries, liver, pancreas, testes & parotid gland. We gave the chemotherapy CHOP to 76.2% (n: 16) & RCHOP in 23.8% (n: 5) patients. We gave the PIM (Prophylactic Intrathecal Methotrexate) to 47.6% (n: 10) patients. There was a complete response in 47.6% (n: 10) patients, partial response in 14.3% (n: 3) and there was progression of disease in 38.1% (n: 8) patients. There was occurrence of Central Nervous System relapse in 81% (n: 17) patients within 6 months after treatment completion. There was systemic disease along with Central Nervous System relapse in 66.6% (n: 14) patients. We noted the isolated Central Nervous System relapse in 33.3% (n: 7) patients. The regimens of second line chemotherapy were HDMTX 23.8% (n: 5), HDMTX/ TRIO IT 14.2% (n: 3), HDMTX/HDAC 9.5% (n: 2), HCVAD 14.2% (n: 3), ICE 19.4% (n: 4), DHAP 4.7% (n: 1), ICE/HDMTX 4.7% (n: 1), none in 9.5% (n: 2). Overall median rate of survival of the patients with Central Nervous System relapse was fifty-four days.

Conclusion: Patients suffering from Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma who were in advanced level, high level of LDH and involvement of extra-nodes at initial appearance are at high danger for relapse of Central Nervous System. About fifty percent patients were present with relapse of Central Nervous System regardless of the primary Central Nervous System prophylaxis. Once there is relapse in the Central Nervous System, there is much adverse diagnosis of these patients.

KEYWORDS: Prophylactic Intrathecal Methotrexate, Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma, Retrospective, Ovaries.

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INTRODUCTION:

The most frequent lymphoid neoplasm among adults is the Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma, responsible for about 32.5% of NHLs detected per year [1]. Involvement of secondary Central Nervous System in the Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma includes an isolated relapse of Central Nervous System or involvement of Central Nervous System with the systemic disease. This uncommon but fatal medical issue is a therapeutic dilemma in administration of Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma [2]. The prevalence of Central Nervous System relapse is 2.2% to 5% in Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma and 1.60% as the isolated relapse of Central Nervous System. Majority of the relapses happen with median time duration of lower than 1 year from the time of initial detection [3-6]. There is strong relationship of enhanced danger for the development of Central Nervous System relapse among patients with increased level of LDH, equal or greater than 2 extra-nodal sites and specific extra-nodal site's involvement [7-9]. There is a valid prognostic model for the prediction of the risk for Central Nervous System relapse with the utilization of 5 clinical factors (age greater than sixty years, level of LDH greater than normal, stage 3 or 4, ECOG PS greater than one and the kidney involvement) [10, 11]. The danger of Central Nervous System relapse is greater in ABC (Activated B-Cell) than GCB (Germinal Center B-Cell) [12, 13]. There is no answer available about the reduction of risk of Central Nervous System relapse with the rituximab [14]. There are no valid proofs that can support any single technique for the Central Nervous System prophylaxis [15]. Intrathecal methotrexate provided minimum one time per systemic therapy cycle has been utilized for many years but high dose of IV-methotrexate based prophylaxis may decrease the prevalence rate of the Central Nervous System relapses [16-19].

METHODOLOGY:

This study is a retrospective research work of conducted on 21 Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma patients who got treatment in Mayo Hospital Lahore We included all the patients of Central Nervous System relapse from 2012 to 2019 in our institute. We collected the information from the database of the hospital and we analyzed the median rate of survival and characteristics of the patients. SPSS V.23 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We performed the descriptive statistics. We represented the categorical data in frequencies and percentages. We used the Chi-square method for the comparison of the baseline characteristics of the patients. P-value of less than 0.05 was the significant one.

RESULTS:

21 patients were the participants of this research work, in which 66.3% (n: 14) were males and 33.7% (n: 7) were female patients. On initial detection of the Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma, median age was 37.4 years with arrange from 27 to 47 years. Ann-Arbor stage of 1-4 was present in 14.3% (n: 3), 9.5% (n: 2), 19% (n: 4) and 57.1% (n: 12) patients, correspondingly. We noted the extra-nodal involvement in 76.2% (n: 16) patients, high level of LDH in 85.7% (n: 18) patients, involvement of bone marrow in 38.1% (n: 8) and bulky disease in 23.8% (n: 5) patients. International Prognostic Index score was one in 19% (n: 4), two in 42.9% (n: 9), three in 38.10% (n: 8) patients. There was gut of extra-nodal sites in 9.10% (n: 2) whereas 4.5% (n: 1) patient with the involvement of these organs was present; cervix, iliac bone, gluteal muscle, ovaries, liver, pancreas, testes & parotid gland. We gave the chemotherapy CHOP to 76.2% (n: 16) & RCHOP in 23.8% (n: 5) patients.

Table-I: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Baseline Characteristics (at time of diagnosis)		Mean / No	± SD / Percent
Age (Years)		37.4	10.14
Gender	Male	14	66.7
	Female	7	33.3
Stage of Disease	I	3	14.3
	II	2	9.5
	III	4	19.0
	IV	12	57.1
LDH	High	18	85.7
	Normal	3	14.3
Extra Nodal Site	None	5	23.8
	Yes	16	76.2
Bulky disease	Yes	5	23.8
	No	16	76.2
Bone Marrow Involvement	Yes	8	38.1
	No	13	61.9

IPI	1	4	19.0
	2	9	42.9
	3	8	38.1

We gave the Prophylactic Intrathecal Methotrexate to 47.6% (n: 10) patients. There was a complete response in 47.6% (n: 10) patients, partial response in 14.3% (n: 3) and there was progression of disease in 38.1% (n: 8) patients. There was occurrence of Central Nervous System relapse in 81% (n: 17) patients within 6 months after treatment completion. There was systemic disease along with Central Nervous System relapse in 66.6% (n: 14) patients. We noted the isolated Central Nervous System relapse in 33.3% (n: 7) patients. The regimens of second line chemotherapy were HDMTX 23.8% (n: 5), HDMTX/ TRIO IT 14.2% (n: 3), HDMTX/HDAC 9.5% (n: 2), HCVAD 14.2% (n: 3), ICE 19.4% (n: 4), DHAP 4.7% (n: 1), ICE/HDMTX 4.7% (n: 1), none 9.5% (n: 2) (Table-2). Overall median rate of survival of the patients present with Central Nervous System relapse was fifty-four days (Figure-1). We found no statistically significant characteristics when measured with the Chi-square method. There was only one alive patient at the time of this treatment.

Table-II: Subsequent Second Line Chemotherapy

Second line Chemotherapy	No	Percentage
HDMTX, High dose methotrexate	5	23.8
HDMTX/TRIO IT, High dose methotrexate/Methotrexate, Cytarabine, Hydrocortisone	3	14.2
HDMTX/HDAC, High dose methotrexate/High dose Ara-C	2	9.5
HCVAD Hyper fractionated cyclophosphamide, vincristine, doxorubicin, dexamethasone	3	14.2
ICE, Ifosphamide, carboplatin, etoposide	4	19.4
DHAP, Dexamethasone, High dose Ara-C, Cisplatin	1	4.7
ICE/HDMTX, Ifosphamide, carboplatin, etoposide/ High dose methotrexate	1	4.7
None	2	9.5
Total	21	100

DISCUSSION:

Majority of the patients of this research work was in advance stage, young and with high level of LDH. There was involvement of only one patient. There was development of the Central Nervous System relapse among patients who got rituximab with the traditional chemotherapy. One systematic study discovered that utilization of rituximab has not influenced the prevalence of the relapse of Central Nervous System as compared with utilization of CHOP [20]. But some research works have displayed some advantages of addition of rituximab to early treatment [21]. Majority of the patients got development of relapse in 6 months of initial treatment that is much similar with the data present in this field [3-6]. In this current research work, isolated Central Nervous System-relapse (33%) is much greater than available information [4, 22]. Detection of population with high risk with support of different models for prognosis like Central Nervous System-IPI [10, 11] and addition of various combinations of Central Nervous System directed treatments may help for the improvement in the survival rate of the patients. No patient of this research work got systemic high-dose methotrexate, many research works advocated this issue [17, 18]. As Central Nervous System relapse has no standard valid treatment [15], various salvage chemotherapeutic regimens were in

use in accordance with the tolerance condition of the patients.

Majority of the patients died in the duration of second line therapy with very short median rate of survival. Median rate of survival in this current research work was very short as compared to the available information which is due to the adverse tolerance condition of our patients, late detection and many other reasons. If there is occurrence of relapse in Central Nervous System, then the high dose treatment with the transplant of the autologous stem cell can improve the overall rate of survival and this approach has displayed the better rate of survival in the isolated Central Nervous System-relapse as compared to the Central Nervous System relapse along with the systemic disease [23].

CONCLUSION:

Patients present with the Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma who were in advanced stage, with high level of LDH and extra-nodal participation at initial appearance are present with high danger for relapse of central nervous system. Once there is relapse in the Central Nervous System, there is very adverse prognosis for these patients.

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